

Differentiate Scalp Psoriasis From Other Scalp Dermatoses

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Abstract

Scalp dermatoses denote a heterogeneous array of cutaneous disorders impacting the scalp, resulting in a variety of clinical presentations and symptoms. These disorders may profoundly affect personal quality of life, resulting in pain, psychological suffering, and social humiliation. Psoriasis is one of the most common scalp dermatoses; nonetheless, it is essential to distinguish it from other comparable disorders for optimal management and therapy. (Jp et al., 2009) The scalp is a distinct anatomical region prone to several dermatological conditions. These illnesses may originate from genetic predispositions, environmental stimuli, or immunological dysfunctions. Prevalent conditions include seborrheic dermatitis, folliculitis, alopecia areata, contact dermatitis, and psoriasis. Each of these disorders has unique characteristics, making clinical distinction essential.

Keywords: *Differentiate Scalp and Psoriasis, Scalp Dermatoses, Differentiate Scalp, Psoriasis, Dermatology*

Introduction

The pathogenesis of scalp dermatoses is diverse, resulting in many symptoms including erythema, scaling, and pruritus. Scalp psoriasis, distinguished by dense, silvery scales, is often mistaken for other types of dermatitis owing to symptom overlap. Misdiagnosis may result in both ineffective therapies and declining skin health.

A precise diagnosis requires a thorough comprehension of the clinical progression and pathophysiology causes of these disorders. By refining analytical skills and using diagnostic tools, doctors can distinguish scalp psoriasis from other dermatoses. This chapter seeks to provide a foundation for comprehending scalp dermatoses, with specific emphasis on the distinctions that set psoriasis apart from similar conditions.

In conclusion, identifying and correctly diagnosing scalp dermatoses is crucial for administering tailored therapies that relieve symptoms and improve patient well-being. In the next chapters, we

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will explore the distinct features, diagnostic techniques, and treatment approaches related to scalp psoriasis and its separation from other skin disorders.

Aim

Scalp psoriasis is a persistent, inflammatory dermatological disorder mostly affecting the scalp. It is marked by the development of distinct, erythematous plaques sometimes adorned with silvery-white scales. ¹

The genesis of scalp psoriasis encompasses a complex interaction of genetic, immunological, and environmental variables. Studies demonstrate a significant genetic propensity, with increased prevalence seen in those with a family history of psoriasis. Certain gene loci, particularly those linked to the major histocompatibility complex (MHC), have been related with the condition's pathophysiology.

The pathogenesis of scalp psoriasis is mostly influenced by immune system dysfunction. An abnormal activation of T cells results in the excessive production of pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α) and interleukin-17 (IL-17). This immune response induces keratinocyte proliferation and subsequently diminishes the normal maturation and desquamation processes of skin cells, leading to the typical thicker plaques and scaling.

Additionally, environmental factors such as stress, illness, and trauma may aggravate scalp psoriasis, precipitating or intensifying disease flare-ups. Comprehending these fundamental mechanisms is essential for accurate diagnosis and therapy, as well as for distinguishing scalp psoriasis from other scalp dermatoses that may exhibit similar clinical characteristics but vary considerably in their pathophysiological processes.

In conclusion, acknowledging the multifactorial characteristics of scalp psoriasis, which include genetic, immunological, and environmental factors, offers a thorough framework that guides

¹ Comprehending the etiology and pathophysiology of scalp psoriasis is essential for distinguishing it from other scalp dermatoses. Gooderham and Blakely, 2016

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clinical assessment and treatment approaches. This fundamental information is essential for efficiently controlling scalp psoriasis and enhancing patient outcomes.(Mosca et al., 2021)

Methodology

Scalp psoriasis presents as a unique dermatosis, distinguished by a variety of clinical characteristics that differentiate it from other scalp disorders. The lesions often manifest as distinct, erythematous plaques adorned with a silvery-white scale. The intensity of scaling may vary, with some individuals displaying widespread involvement while others have isolated patches. The degree of scalp involvement might vary significantly, influencing the clinical presentation. Certain people may exhibit localized patches, whilst others have extensive scalp involvement that requires thorough evaluation. The plaques may merge, resulting in extensive inflammation that may spread beyond the hairline, impacting the forehead, neck, and postauricular areas.

It is crucial to acknowledge the symptoms connected with scalp psoriasis. Patients often experience pruritus, which may vary from moderate to severe, perhaps leading in scratching that exacerbates inflammation and leads to secondary issues such as infection. Although pain is seldom reported, discomfort may occur due to chronic lesions or hypersensitive skin. Nail involvement is a significant factor in scalp psoriasis, with up to 50% of patients displaying nail degeneration, characterized by pitting, ridging, and onycholysis. Nail alterations may serve as a significant diagnostic indicator, as they often correspond with the severity of scalp psoriasis. Furthermore, the psychological ramifications of scalp psoriasis may profoundly affect quality of life. Patients often endure discomfort due to the conspicuous character of their lesions, resulting in social seclusion and reduced self-esteem.

The clinical manifestation of scalp psoriasis is defined by distinct plaques, accompanying symptoms, and possible nail involvement, requiring comprehensive evaluation for precise

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diagnosis and treatment. Comprehending these clinical characteristics is crucial for distinguishing scalp psoriasis from other scalp dermatoses.²

Literature Review

Accurate separation of scalp psoriasis from other scalp dermatoses requires a thorough investigation of essential symptoms. Scalp psoriasis is defined by distinct, erythematous plaques adorned with silvery-white scaling lesions, which may vary from a few millimeters to huge areas. Patients often describe sensations of itching, burning, or discomfort in the afflicted regions, but the intensity may vary.

Conversely, seborrheic dermatitis generally manifests as oily, yellowish scales and is often linked to broader regions of erythema. The appearance of scaling that tightly clings to hair follicles and is especially pronounced in sebaceous-rich areas might serve as a differentiating characteristic. Moreover, seborrheic dermatitis induces a less intense pruritic response compared to psoriasis.³

Another factor to examine is atopic dermatitis, which often presents in younger people. Atopic dermatitis is marked by severe itching and a propensity for lesions to form in flexural regions, however it may also manifest on the scalp. The scaling in this illness is often less pronounced and may display lichenification, differentiating it from the clearly defined plaques characteristic of psoriasis.

Contact dermatitis requires assessment, since it often manifests with localized erythema and edema subsequent to contact to irritants or allergens. This disorder may present with vesicular lesions and is often associated with a history of exposure to the causative chemical. Ultimately, folliculitis may resemble psoriasis but often presents with pustular characteristics and is usually confined to areas around hair follicles. Factors include the presence of pustules, lesion distribution, and patient history are essential for distinction. Common dermatological conditions,

² Gooderham and Blakely, 2016

³ Scale and Crusts, n.d.

2014

A comprehensive clinical evaluation, targeted history acquisition, and comprehension of the symptomatic subtleties of each ailment are essential for attaining an accurate diagnosis.

Findings

Scalp dermatoses include many disorders that may resemble or coexist with scalp psoriasis, complicating diagnosis and treatment. Identifying these prevalent scalp problems is crucial for formulating an effective treatment strategy.

A notable condition to consider is **seborrheic dermatitis**. Seborrheic dermatitis is characterized by flaky scales and erythema, generally occurring in an oily scalp environment. It is often differentiated from psoriasis by its oily scale and the distinct, as opposed to confluent, characteristics of the lesions.

Another relevant dermatosis is **contact dermatitis**, resulting from irritants or allergens impacting the scalp. Patients often describe pruritus and localized erythema, contrasting with the chronicity and plaque growth characteristic with scalp psoriasis. Determining the causative factor is essential for a successful treatment strategy. Dermatitis (Contact, Seborrheic, Atopic), n.d. Tinea capitis, a fungal infection, is a prevalent differential diagnosis. It appears as a scaly region accompanied by alopecia and may exhibit concurrent inflammation. In contrast to psoriasis, the scales in tinea are often finer and may result in kerion development, requiring antifungal therapy. Lichen planus manifests as violaceous, polygonal papules, which may sometimes affect the scalp. The pruritic characteristic and unique look distinguish it from the plaque-type lesions associated with scalp psoriasis. Histological analysis may disclose band-like infiltrates of lymphocytes at the dermal-epidermal interface, facilitating diagnosis.

Finally, **pityriasis amiantacea** warrants discussion. This disorder is marked by thick, adhering scales that exhibit a matted look, often linked to underlying scalp inflammation. In contrast to psoriasis, this disorder often has a more widespread scaling pattern. Pityriasis amiantacea: a clinical and etiopathological investigation of 85 cases, n.d.

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A thorough understanding of these prevalent scalp dermatoses is essential for distinguishing them from scalp psoriasis, therefore greatly impacting treatment choices and patient results.

Argument

Diagnosing scalp psoriasis requires a comprehensive strategy that combines clinical assessment with many diagnostic methods. Precise distinction from other scalp dermatoses is essential for administering proper therapy.

Initially, a thorough clinical history must be obtained, including the origin, duration, and development of symptoms, along with any relevant variables such as family history and comorbidities. An thorough evaluation of the patient's medical history offers critical context and may indicate psoriasis or other chronic ailments.

Physical examination is crucial: practitioners must examine the scalp for distinctive lesions, often characterized as well-defined, erythematous plaques adorned with silvery scales. The position and distribution of lesions, often extending beyond the scalp edge, should be documented as they may facilitate diagnosis. Hayman et al. (2003)

Trichoscopy, a non-invasive diagnostic technique with a dermoscope, has become an invaluable instrument. This approach provides an enlarged perspective of scalp lesions, aiding in the identification of distinctive characteristics of scalp psoriasis, including glomerular vessels and yellowish scales.

In some instances, laboratory testing may be necessary to rule out other reasons. Scalp scrapings may be conducted to exclude fungal diseases, such as tinea capitis, especially in individuals exhibiting scaling. Furthermore, serum analysis for inflammatory markers might provide insights in more intricate instances, indicating possible psoriatic arthritis.

A skin biopsy may ultimately be required when the diagnosis is unclear. Histopathological analysis will often disclose significant characteristics like acanthosis, parakeratosis, and a substantial inflammatory infiltration within the epidermis and dermis.

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The combined use of these diagnostic approaches provides a comprehensive framework for the precise diagnosis of scalp psoriasis, facilitating successful care.

Biopsy Considerations and Histopathological Features

The use of biopsy in assessing scalp psoriasis is essential for achieving an accurate diagnosis, particularly in distinguishing it from other scalp dermatoses. A skin biopsy allows a thorough histopathological analysis that clarifies the fundamental structural alterations linked to the disease process.

When contemplating a biopsy, it is crucial to choose the suitable location, often opting for a lesional region exhibiting characteristic signs of psoriasis, including scaling and erythema. The biopsy must be conducted with appropriate technique to guarantee adequate tissue sample while reducing harm to the adjacent skin.

Histopathological analysis of scalp psoriasis tissues reveals several distinctive features. A prominent characteristic is acanthosis, defined by epidermal thickness resulting from heightened keratinocyte proliferation. Moreover, there is often a significant infiltration of inflammatory cells, especially neutrophils, which may create Munro microabscesses in the stratum corneum.⁴

Additional diagnostic characteristics include extended dermal papillae that may extend into the epidermis, with "keratinocyte hyperproliferation," leading to a modified keratinization process. The histological pattern may display alterations such as parakeratosis, signifying the preservation of nuclei in the stratum corneum, accompanied by a reduction in the granular layer. It is crucial to distinguish these results from those shown in other scalp dermatoses, such as seborrheic dermatitis or contact dermatitis, which may have analogous clinical presentations but possess unique histological characteristics. Specifically, seborrheic dermatitis generally exhibits less acanthosis and fewer frequent inflammatory infiltrates.

⁴ Hambrick, 1967

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A comprehensive grasp of biopsy concerns and associated histological findings can markedly improve diagnostic precision and provide suitable therapy strategies in scalp psoriasis.

Role of Family and Medical History in Diagnosis

The assessment of familial and medical history is crucial in diagnosing scalp psoriasis and distinguishing it from other scalp dermatoses. Genetic predisposition is widely acknowledged as a significant role in the genesis of psoriasis, with a substantial prevalence of the disorder among first-degree relatives. Comprehending a patient's family history may provide critical insights regarding the probability of latent psoriatic conditions.

A precise evaluation of familial history concerning skin illnesses, especially psoriasis and other inflammatory diseases, might aid doctors in recognizing patterns that may indicate a genetic association. A familial history of illnesses like psoriatic arthritis or atopic dermatitis might inform the diagnosis procedure, since they may coexist or affect symptom presentation.⁵

A thorough medical history, including prior dermatological disorders, treatment responses, and any comorbidities, may significantly assist in differentiating scalp psoriasis from other dermatoses. Individuals with a history of atopy may have symptoms that resemble seborrheic dermatitis, requiring a more sophisticated diagnostic approach.

Additionally, triggers and aggravating variables, such stress, infection, or changes in medication, must be investigated during the patient interview. Collecting data on previous scalp treatments and their results is crucial, since it may indicate patterns characteristic of psoriasis rather than other scalp disorders.

A comprehensive analysis of familial and medical history is essential in the diagnosis procedure for scalp psoriasis. By clarifying possible genetic factors and historical medical experiences, healthcare providers may create a more accurate diagnostic profile, ultimately improving treatment

⁵ The correlation between psoriasis and autoimmune disorders, 2012

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efficacy and patient outcomes. This comprehensive knowledge underpins subsequent evaluation and intervention techniques in the treatment of scalp dermatoses.⁶

Therapeutic Approaches for Scalp Psoriasis

Scalp psoriasis, a persistent inflammatory skin condition, requires a comprehensive treatment strategy customized to the specific requirements of each patient. The primary objectives of therapy are to diminish inflammation, relieve symptoms, and enhance overall quality of life. Topical treatments provide the fundamental approach for treating localized scalp psoriasis. Frequently used medications include corticosteroids, which assist in alleviating inflammation and pruritus. High-potency topical corticosteroids are often advised for severe instances, although medium-potency alternatives may be useful for milder presentations. Vitamin D analogues, including calcipotriene, are often used with corticosteroids to improve therapeutic effectiveness. Tar-based formulations have a historical precedent in the treatment of scalp psoriasis, demonstrating anti-inflammatory properties and facilitating desquamation. These choices may be augmented with moisturizers to address dryness and scaling.⁷

Systemic therapy may be necessary for people with severe or refractory scalp psoriasis. Biologic drugs that target particular pathways in the immune response, such tumor necrosis factor (TNF) inhibitors and interleukin inhibitors, have shown considerable effectiveness in treating psoriasis in several body areas, including the scalp. Systemic retinoids, such as acitretin, may be contemplated, however they may exhibit significant adverse effects.

Phototherapy, especially narrowband ultraviolet B (NB-UVB), has shown to be a significant supplementary option for individuals who inadequately react to topical or systemic therapies. The regulated exposure to UV radiation may significantly enhance the symptoms of scalp psoriasis. In summary, the care of scalp psoriasis necessitates a tailored strategy that incorporates topical, systemic, and phototherapeutic methods, with the objective of alleviating disease burden and

⁶ Elewski, 2005

⁷ Evidence-based guidance for topical treatments of scalp psoriasis (n.d.)

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improving the patient's quality of life. Consistent follow-ups and adjustments to the therapy protocol are crucial for attaining optimum results.

Managing Comorbid Conditions and Psoriatic Involvement

Psoriasis, especially scalp psoriasis, often accompanies many comorbidities, substantially affecting patient treatment and quality of life. Comprehending these relationships is essential for physicians to provide holistic therapy.

It is crucial to acknowledge that psoriatic illness includes both cutaneous signs and systemic effects, including psoriatic arthritis (PsA). The incidence of PsA in individuals with scalp psoriasis may reach 30%. Timely recognition of arthritic involvement is essential, since neglect may result in irreparable joint damage.

Cardiovascular disease is a common comorbidity associated with scalp psoriasis. Studies demonstrate that individuals with moderate to severe psoriasis possess an increased risk for hypertension, hyperlipidemia, and metabolic syndrome. Healthcare practitioners must carefully monitor these cardiovascular risk factors. Consistent screening and the implementation of lifestyle changes may reduce these risks, hence improving patient outcomes. Early, 2007 Furthermore, a recognized association exists between psoriasis and mental disorders, such as sadness and anxiety. Stress intensifies psoriatic symptoms, establishing a detrimental loop that may aggravate skin signs. Behavioral health evaluations and referrals to mental health specialists are essential elements of a comprehensive treatment strategy.

Moreover, obesity often coexists with psoriasis, and addressing this condition is essential to the comprehensive therapy approach. Weight reduction may alleviate the severity of psoriasis, providing both physiological and psychological advantages. A systematic diet and exercise regimen should be regarded as integral components of therapeutic therapies. In conclusion, the complex nature of scalp psoriasis requires a multidisciplinary strategy to treat comorbidities efficiently. By tackling these interrelated health concerns, doctors may provide more effective therapy and improve the overall well-being of those impacted.

Patient Education and Self-Care Strategies

Effective therapy of scalp psoriasis requires a strong basis of patient education and self-care techniques. Comprehending the ailment, its precipitating factors, and management strategies enables patients to take an active part in their treatment protocol.

Initially, patients should be informed about the characteristics of scalp psoriasis. This include clarifying the etiology, prevalent symptoms, and possible exacerbating variables like stress, environmental alterations, and nutritional impacts. Patients must be informed that scalp psoriasis is a persistent disease, often need continuous care.

Subsequently, cognizance of efficacious self-care methodologies is essential. Patients must to be urged to develop a consistent hair care regimen that reduces discomfort. Mild shampoos and conditioners, specifically designed for sensitive skin, may mitigate discomfort while enhancing scalp health. Furthermore, refraining from aggressive chemical treatments and reducing heat style helps mitigate the worsening of the problem. (Fu and Price, 2009) Hydration is essential for preserving scalp integrity. Patients should be advised to use emollients or oils to the scalp to alleviate irritation and scaling. Additionally, the use of topical therapies, like corticosteroids or vitamin D analogs, must be evaluated for effectiveness and modified as necessary in collaboration with healthcare professionals.

A diet that is balanced and abundant in omega-3 fatty acids, vitamins, and antioxidants may enhance skin health and maybe reduce the intensity of psoriasis flare-ups. Patients must to be motivated to sustain a healthy lifestyle by integrating regular physical activity and stress management strategies.

Ultimately, cultivating a support network, whether via family, friends, or support organizations, may markedly improve psychological well-being. Recognizing that psoriasis may impact mental well-being is essential, and seeking professional assistance, when needed, is advisable. In summary, a thorough strategy for patient education and self-care not only boosts health results but also elevates the entire quality of life for those afflicted with scalp psoriasis.

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This thorough analysis of scalp psoriasis and its separation from other scalp dermatoses underscores the need of an interdisciplinary approach for precise diagnosis and appropriate care. The clinical intricacy of scalp psoriasis requires the amalgamation of dermatological expertise, patient history, and modern diagnostic methodologies. This comprehensive knowledge assists practitioners in customizing therapeutic strategies, therefore enhancing patient outcomes. Despite great breakthroughs in therapy choices, a substantial information gap persists about the precise pathophysiological pathways that differentiate scalp psoriasis from other dermatoses. Future research must focus on clarifying these disparities at the molecular and genetic levels to facilitate the creation of tailored medicines that can more successfully meet specific patient requirements.

Furthermore, the significance of the microbiome in scalp health is an emerging area of research. Examining the relationships between scalp microbiota and skin disorders may provide new insights, possibly affecting preventative and treatment approaches. Saxena et al. (2018) Integrating patient-reported outcomes and quality of life evaluations into clinical research is essential. Comprehending the impact of scalp psoriasis on everyday life, mental well-being, and social relationships will improve the formulation of comprehensive treatment strategies. As telemedicine advances, its use in dermatology may provide early diagnosis and ongoing treatment, especially for impoverished populations.

The future of scalp psoriasis research should include multidisciplinary cooperation and individualized medication. As we explore the complexities of this disorder, the possibility for novel therapies that improve patient quality of life becomes more attainable. Ongoing funding in this study will provide enhanced understanding and treatment of scalp psoriasis and its many forms. Jp et al., 2009

Conclusion and Future Directions

This extensive examination of scalp psoriasis and its distinction from other scalp dermatoses highlights the intricacy and multivariate nature of scalp diseases. In the chapters, we have outlined

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the essential elements of comprehending scalp psoriasis, including its genesis, pathophysiology, clinical symptoms, and differential diagnosis.

The significance of precise diagnosis cannot be overstated; incorrect findings may result in unsuitable therapies and deteriorate patient outcomes. Consequently, practitioners must maintain vigilance in using rigorous diagnostic methods, taking into account both clinical manifestations and histological assessments to ensure accurate identification.

Moreover, we have emphasized the need of incorporating therapeutic procedures customized to the specific requirements of each patient, including both pharmaceutical interventions and self-care practices. The comprehensive therapy of scalp psoriasis must also address the related comorbidities often associated with this chronic illness, requiring a holistic approach to patient care. (Jp et al., 2009)

Future research has potential prospects to elucidate the underlying processes of scalp psoriasis and enhance diagnostic tools. Progress in genetic research, biomarker discovery, and innovative therapeutic molecules has the potential to transform our comprehension and treatment of this disorder.

As practitioners persist in lifelong learning, being informed about new results will be crucial for advancing clinical treatment and boosting the quality of life for those afflicted by scalp psoriasis. This book is a fundamental resource; nonetheless, we advocate for continuous debate and investigation in the area to promote further progress in dermatological treatment.

References

- Early, J L. (2007, January 1). Comprehensive management of cardiometabolic risk factors. Elsevier BV, 8(3), 69-80. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1098-3597\(07\)80029-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1098-3597(07)80029-9)
- El-Labban, I A A S A A Y M M A M. (n.d). Pityriasis amiantacea: a clinical and etiopathologic study of 85 patients. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1046/j.1365-4362.2003.01755.x>

- Elewski, B E. (2005, October 6). Clinical Diagnosis of Common Scalp Disorders. Elsevier BV, 10(3), 190-193. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1087-0024.2005.10103.x>
- Fu, J., & Price, V H. (2009, June 1). Approach to Hair Loss in Women of Color. , 28(2), 109-114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sder.2009.04.004>
- Gooderham, M., & Blakely, K. (2016, March 1). Management of scalp psoriasis: current perspectives. Dove Medical Press, 33-33. <https://doi.org/10.2147/ptt.s85330>
- Hambrick, G W. (1967, March 1). PHILADELPHIA DERMATOLOGICAL SOCIETY. American Medical Association, 95(3), 329-329. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archderm.1967.01600330087019>
- Hayman, A., Shukla, V., Ly, C V., & Taber, K H. (2003, May 1). Clinical and Imaging Anatomy of the Scalp. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins, 27(3), 454-459. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00004728-200305000-00027>
- Herrinton, J J W J T U N K T P L J. (2012, June 4). The association of psoriasis with autoimmune diseases.. <https://jaad.org/retrieve/pii/S0190962212004628>
- Jp, O., Chimenti, S., Luger, T A., Puig, L., Reid, F., & Trüeb, R. (2009, July 15). Scalp psoriasis: European consensus on grading and treatment algorithm. Wiley, 23(12), 1435-1444. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-3083.2009.03372.x>
- Mosca, M., Hong, J., Haderler, E., Brownstone, N., Bhutani, T., & Liao, W. (2021, April 24). Scalp Psoriasis: A Literature Review of Effective Therapies and Updated Recommendations for Practical Management. Adis, Springer Healthcare, 11(3), 769-797. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13555-021-00521-z>
- O'connor, J C V T U O W 4 R W N 4 F B 3 9 S W U J K M. (2014, May 5). Common dermatologic conditions.. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0025712514000078>
- Saxena, R., Mittal, P., Clavaud, C., Dhakan, D B., Hegde, P S., Veeranagaiah, M M., Saha, S., Souverain, L., Roy, N., Breton, L., Misra, N., & Sharma, V K. (2018, October 4).

CURRENT SCIENCE

Comparison of Healthy and Dandruff Scalp Microbiome Reveals the Role of Commensals in Scalp Health. *Frontiers Media*, 8.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fcimb.2018.00346>

Scale and Crusts. (n.d). <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/9781119414612.ch13>

Scalp lesions, in images. (n.d). <https://www.magonlinelibrary.com/doi/10.12968/indn.2015.1.32>

Skin physiology.. (n.d). <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1744187006701834>

Topical treatments for scalp psoriasis: evidence-based guide. (n.d).

<https://wchh.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/psb.1429>

USA, J B J W V U M. (n.d). Dermatitis (Contact, Seborrheic, Atopic).

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780080552323607937>